

TF-IDF Based Fake News Classification: A Lightweight Machine Learning Study with Linear SVM Dominance

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Abstract

Due to the daily circulation of fake news on online media now become a significant challenge for society, shaping public views and spreading fake information. Detecting fake news automatically by using machine learning has become a significant area of research. This study shows an automated fake news identification system leveraging NLP combined with a machine learning approach. A publicly sourced Kaggle dataset comprising both authentic and fabricated news articles was utilized for training and evaluation purposes. The textual data is first pre-processed to remove inconsistencies in the data and further prepare it for analysis. To convert raw text into a format suitable for classification, TF-IDF vectorization was applied, which assigns numerical importance scores to terms proportional to their document level frequency. In order to determine what is not real news from real news, different classification models have been considered four classifiers: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and Linear SVM. Experimental results revealed that from all four evaluated classifiers, like Linear SVM, achieves higher accuracy with 99.51%. Consequently, traditional ML techniques combined with TF-IDF proved to be highly useful in identifying fake news, showing the desired result of a machine learning approach for misleading detection

Keywords: *Fake News Detection, Machine Learning, TF-IDF, Comparative Classification, Linear SVM, Natural Language Processing, Misinformation Detection*

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of online news platforms and social media has sudden accelerated unverified information circulation. People nowadays get the news and share the misinformation very quickly. However, these platforms are used to spread fake and half-informed information. This fake news influences people's thinking, creates confusion, and might reduce trust in the real news sources. As per this, the detection of fake news now becomes the import part in today's modern world, identifying fake news now becomes a major challenge in our modern society.

As mentioned earlier, the fake news detection is checking through manual fact-checking and rule-based systems. Using this method takes a lot of time, consumes more time for analysing whether the information is fake or not and is also not suitable for handling large amounts of online content. Recent advancements in AI and ML have enabled automated systems capable of identifying misinformation at scale, overcoming the limitations of manual verification, as it reduces time and handles a large amount of data at once. Deep learning models like CNN, RNN, and transfer-based models can understand language patterns and context, which is faster and helps to detect more accurately whether a given article is authentic or fabricated

Several recent investigations have established that lightweight SVM classifiers utilising TF-IDF representations achieve accuracy levels comparable to computationally intensive transformer models such as BERT [10][11].

In previous years, the large language models have shown excellent performance in understanding human language. These models can efficiently understand the meaning of text and the contextual relationship, rather than traditional methods. As a result, they are useful for fake news detection. Although there are many existing systems facing the problems such as poor performance on new data, a lack of robustness, and much more difficult in explaining predictions.

Although generative AI driven approaches for instant fake news identification have gained research attention, their practical implementation is constrained by architectural complexity and elevated computational overhead [12].

To solve these issues, this study proposes a misinformation detection framework combining machine learning with TF-IDF. This technique transforms textual content into numerical representations by identifying the important words. This machine learning approach analyzes the textual features to increase the overall performance of the model. These experiments are conducted with the available benchmark to produce the desired result of the proposed system. In the current study, the emphasis will be laid on exploring several lightweight classification models like Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and Linear SVM with feature representation by TF-IDF in order to find out the most suitable strategy for the detection of fake news.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With the swift hike of the like the social media and digital platforms. Nowadays, the spread of fake news has become a more serious problem. As a result, many researchers focused on making automation systems to identify the fake or false leading information. Moreover, these systems are developed for the simple machine learning model to advance deep learning and large language model (LLM) based approaches.

Zheng et al. [1] offers a novel approach for detecting fake news through an explanation-based multi-modal architecture that takes into account both textual as well as visual information in order to detect fake news. The algorithm utilizes large vision-language pre-trained models along with smaller pre-trained language models to generate rationale behind every decision taken. The model was extremely successful when tested on Weibo and PHEME databases and managed to outperform all other recent algorithms considerably. There is something positive about this paper in the form of an interpretable system embedded within the model, which may be used by the users to understand why a particular news has been labeled as being fake news. However, there is one drawback with regard to the computational complexity of the model due to the requirement to call large models more than once.

Tahmasebi et al. [2], the authors presented an algorithm that solves the weaknesses of adversarial attack problems associated with emotion manipulation during the fake news classification process. Tahmasebi et al. developed a method for recognizing emotion manipulation without sentiment analysis through the

application of a pre-trained language model that underwent fine-tuning during the experimental work. According to the experimental findings, it can be argued that the algorithms are more susceptible to emotion manipulation than the credibility of document information. In terms of accuracy compared to other algorithms, their method performed better in PolitiFact and GossipCop datasets.

Bashaddadh et al. [3] was done systematically, taking 90 sources into consideration, primarily focused on the problem of identifying fake news. What concerns the measures undertaken to combat the fake news mentioned above, in addition to the traditional approaches of machine learning, Bashaddadh et al. utilized more complex methods such as CNN, LSTM model, and transformers. Thus, according to the results obtained by the researchers, one may conclude that out of all the methods used for identifying fake news, the latter methods showed better results. Several trends have been revealed by the researchers in the sphere under discussion.

Arega et al. [4] was aimed at establishing whether there is any fake news present in the information-poor Afaan Oromo language. During the literature review conducted, various traditional, deep learning, and mixed models applicable for small-sized data sets produced using social networking websites such as Facebook were analyzed. Although a couple of sophisticated models had a lot of promises, all the other models failed in providing viable solutions due to inadequate data availability and language complexity.

In this respect, the study carried out by Ahmed et al. [5] involved the use of machine learning approaches to detect fake news stories. Here, the approach analyzed the application of n-gram fusion methods along with conventional classification models. As such, the results showed excellent performance in terms of the TF-IDF, logistic regression, and linear SVM techniques.

Shu et al. [6] conducted a literature review in regards to fake news detection in social media contexts. According to Shu et al., the current methodologies have been categorized into two types of classifications. These include knowledge-based approaches and style-based approaches. Besides, Shu et al. developed a valuable database called FakeNewsNet, considering the social context as well.

It is noted by Riedel et al. [7] that they have created a dataset referred to as the Fake News Challenge (FNC-1) and experimented with various machine learning techniques on this task for recognizing stances concerning fake news. It turns out that the application of gradient boosted decision tree and convolutional neural network is quite effective.

The benchmark data set LIAR was provided by Wang [8], used for detecting false information, containing over 12,000 statements manually labeled using Politifact. According to Wang [8], different machine learning and deep learning algorithms were tested against the provided data set, and results showed that meta-data features can be very important in achieving higher performance.

Granik and Mesyura [9] were among the first to utilize naive Bayes classifiers in order to solve the issue of detecting fake news articles. Their straightforward method proved to be fairly accurate while also demonstrating the feasibility of using probabilistic models without relying on extensive computing resources.

From the reviewed literature, it is very clear that the fake news detection has progressed continuously in recent years. Along with that it is the noticeable direction from traditional machine learning techniques to deep learning and large language model-based systems. Researchers are continuously pointing on multimodal analysis, explainability, and robustness against opposing attacks. Although many existing approaches still suffering from high

computational cost, lack of transparency, and limited adaptability to new domains, and vulnerability to manipulation.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research shows the experimental approach to build up fake news detection using machine learning techniques. The main objective of this research is to design a lightweight and efficient model that can classify news articles as real or fake. The research methodology includes the corpus acquisition, text normalisation, feature engineering, classifier training and evaluation. This model is implemented in the online Google Colab environment.

A. Dataset

This study shows the fake news dataset, which is taken from Kaggle, for model training and evaluation. Each entry is pre-labelled as either authentic or fabricated. Each article includes information like the title and the main content. In the dataset, there are two main files, where one file holds fabricated articles while the other contains verified content. These files are combined into a single dataset for smoother use. Before performing the Machine learning, fake news is given as the label 0, whereas the real news given as the label 1.

B. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing plays an important part in performing machine learning. In data preprocessing, we clean our data, perform the EDA Exploratory Data Analysis, where we find the missing values and outliers to make a good fit for the training the ml models. In the research, several steps were taken to normalize the text and improve the quality of the dataset before performing the feature extraction

Steps:

- Convert all text to lower case
- Remove the punctuation and special characters
- Remove stop words
- Tokenizing the text into words
- Cleaning the unwanted spaces and symbols

C. Feature Extraction (TF-IDF)

Since the machine learning models did not manually convert the textual data into a numerical format, we need some machine learning techniques to transform textual data into structured numerical data. As in the research, we use the technique of Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency, which converts raw text into structured numerical vectors. TF-IDF is a technique that utilizes mathematical computation to transform texts into numbers by computing the score of each term according to its discriminative value within a given document compared to others. How often the word appear frequently in a document, but hardly in other documents, receive high importance scores. This model helps to identify the important patterns within the news article. The TF-IDF is applied to the training dataset and then afterward used to transform the testing dataset. This technique corresponds to the findings provided by Karimi et al. [13] on the effectiveness of the TF-IDF characteristics in differentiating for various conventional classifiers.

D. Model Training and Comparative Analysis

After going through the feature extraction (TF-IDF), the resulting feature matrix was fed into each classifier. Initially, Logistic Regression was selected to perform the machine learning. This algorithm is selected due to its performance in text classification and requires relatively low computational resources. The dataset is divided into the two main parts, where the 80% is the training section, along with that further 20% is the testing section, where we perform the testing on the training data and checks how well it perform and what its gives the accuracy after training the model

and to learn patterns separating fabricated from authentic content, implemented via Python's Scikit-learn library.

In addition, to prove the efficiency of the model that we have proposed, three other classifiers namely Random Forest Classifier, Naive Bayes Classifier, and Linear SVM are also used to conduct a comparative analysis using their feature vectors represented by TF-IDF. Both the models have been trained using the same feature vectors but in different data training and testing sets. This is performed using Python Scikit learn library in Google Colab.

E. Model Evaluation

Performance evaluations of all four classifiers were carried out using the testing dataset that consisted of 8,984 samples, taking into consideration the four criteria as shown below. Analysis and comparison of all four classifiers were conducted, and the results are shown in Table I below. Linear SVM is the most accurate classifier at 99.51%, followed by the random forest classifier with an accuracy of 99.01%. Logistic regression is third with an accuracy rate of 98.61%, and last is the naïve Bayes classifier with 93.67%.

FINAL MODEL COMPARISON TABLE				
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	98.61	98.61	98.61	98.61
Random Forest	99.01	99.01	99.01	99.01
Naive Bayes	93.67	93.67	93.67	93.67
Linear SVM	99.51	99.51	99.51	99.51

Figure 1. Performance metrics and accuracy outcomes of the trained news verification classifier.

Figure 2. Prediction outcome matrix illustrating the classification behaviour of the developed classifier.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

In the designed approach, each successive stage takes its inputs from the previous one. Initially, news articles are cleaned through the process of lowering text to lowercase, removing punctuations, and deleting stop words. The resulting text is further converted to a matrix using TF-IDF vectorization before being fed to the classifier for generating output in the form of either fake(0) or

real(1)

Figure 3. Overview of the developed pipeline for automated news authenticity classification.

V. RESULTS

In the following section, we will focus on outcomes of experiments assessing classifier performance on fake news identification through TF-IDF-based feature engineering. There are 44,919 news data in the dataset, of which 23,502 news data are fake, whereas the remaining 21,417 news data are real.

The following approaches have been adopted for determining the efficiency of the recommended model:

Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 Score. From the output provided in Table I under the Model Evaluation section, among all the classifiers used including Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest, the top-performing model was Linear SVM, achieving 99.51% accuracy.

The classification report is presented in Figure 1, offering a granular breakdown of precision, recall, and F1-score across both categories. As per the result evaluated after training the model, we will see that the classifier correctly distinguished fabricated from genuine articles with minimal misclassification

Moreover, Figure 2 presents the confusion matrix, providing a granular view of prediction outcomes. The confusion matrix confirmed strong model performance, with 4,662 fake articles and 4,197 real articles correctly classified, leaving only a negligible number of misclassified samples.. This research aimed that the machine learning approach proves highly capable of separating genuine reporting from fabricated content

VI. DISCUSSION

Based on the experimental results, it is evident that machine learning models combined with TF-IDF are extremely effective in identifying fake news, which aligns with the findings of Hassan et al. [14]. It is evident that the use of machine learning models together with TF-IDF is extremely effective in spotting any fake news, which coincides with the work carried out by Hassan et al. [14], who examined the effectiveness of using TF-IDF to detect fake news. Among the four different models tested, the Linear SVM model demonstrated peak classification performance at 99.51% accuracy, making it the most suitable choice for analyzing text datasets built using the TF-IDF method. The Random Forest algorithm came in second place with an accuracy of 99.01%. Although it is a complex classifier that usually prevents overfitting problems, the performance level achieved by the model is acceptable. Additionally, the Logistic Regression algorithm produced reliable results with an accuracy of 98.61%. However, despite being a fairly simple algorithm, its performance level can be attributed to effective feature selection techniques.

One key lesson from the research is that there is no need for deep learning models in order for the lightweight models, all four, to perform well. This means that the recommended model would be very useful when applied in reality because it will efficiently work under the pressure of limited resources. Despite the high-quality language processing skills of BERT and GPT, they are more expensive than traditional models. This is also reflected by Jethwa et al. [12] and Karim [10], who noted that despite advancements in generative AI and transformers, traditional models prove more appropriate under computational restrictions., when they state that despite advancements made in the fields of generative AI and transformers, the traditional models prove more appropriate in situations involving computational restrictions.

The possible research areas for the future may include application of ensemble learning, which contains multiple classifiers, experiments involving algorithms with datasets in various languages, and experimentation with data sources that are not purely textual data like meta data and sociological data.

VII. CONCLUSION

This work evaluated four classical ML classifiers on their capacity to automatically identify fake news through automatic classification after feature extraction based on the TF-IDF method. The experimental evaluation was conducted on a Kaggle-sourced corpus of 44,919 news records, of which approximately 80% were allocated for training while the remaining 20% served as the held-out test split.

Linear SVM performed the best among all classification algorithms, giving an accuracy score of 99.51%, followed by Random Forests with 99.01%, then came Logistic Regression with 98.61%, and lastly Naive Bayes with an accuracy score of 93.67%. All the aforementioned results show that ML can function well even without the implementation of deep learning technology.

Moreover, this investigation contributes to the existing body of literature which proposes that even elementary models, such as the Logistic Regression model, may yield very impressive results when used in combination with proper feature selection techniques in the field of classification. Possible areas of future investigation could involve cross-domain learning, investigating news articles written in various languages, as well as additional socio-contextual factors.

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